

Machinability of austenitic stainless steels 304/304L for medical applications

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Abstract: Austenitic stainless steels 304 and 304L are widely used for their excellent properties, including corrosion resistance and toughness. However, their machinability is challenging due to high work hardening and low heat conductivity. This study examines the effect of alloy composition, microstructure, and surface integrity on the machinability of 304 and 304L during turning processes. Variations in alloy composition showed minimal effect on machinability, whereas micro-hardness and subsurface residual stress significantly influenced cutting forces, surface roughness, and tool wear. Specifically, machinability worsened with hardness exceeding 350 HV and compressive residual stress below -130 MPa.

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I. Introduction

Machining austenitic stainless steels 304 and 304L is essential across various industries including automotive, aerospace, medical, and food processing due to their high durability, corrosion resistance, and biocompatibility. However, these steels present machining challenges, including low thermal conductivity and significant work hardening, which result in high cutting forces, elevated temperatures, and excessive tool wear, impacting cost and surface quality

Research has explored various aspects of machinability for these steels. Elsheikh et al. [1] and Butola et al. [2] investigated how turning conditions affect the microstructure and mechanical properties of machined surfaces. Shreemoy et al. [3] found that optimal machining parameters for 304 stainless steel involve low feed speeds and moderate depths of cut. Hamdan et al. [4] identified depth of cut as a crucial factor in cutting performance, while Zhang et al. [5] developed a model to predict microstructural changes and residual stress.

This study investigates how variations in alloy compositions and surface integrity of stainless steels 304 and 304L affect machinability during turning operations. By examining different production batches and manufacturers, the research aims to correlate alloy compositions and surface conditions with machinability indicators such as cutting forces, surface roughness, tool wear, and chip morphology.

II. Material and methods

Six variants of austenitic stainless steels 304 and 304L, in cylindrical bars ($\Phi 22$ mm, L 3 m), were sourced from five manufacturers. The variants were chosen for their relevance in producing a medical instrument. Variants 1-4 were soft annealed and cold drawn, while variants 5 and 6 were peeled, with variant 5 being the peeled counterpart of variant 4. Prior to machining, the microstructure, residual

stress, and surface micro-hardness were examined. Machining trials were conducted on a Haas-TL1 CNC lathe using a Sandvik Coromant cutting insert (Fig. 1). Cutting forces were measured with a KISTLER 9257B dynamometer. The study involved roughing and finishing operations at three feed rates (0.08, 0.15, and 0.3 mm/rev) with a constant cutting speed of 80 m/min. Evaluations included surface roughness, cutting forces, tool wear, residual stress, microhardness, and chip morphology, with tests repeated for statistical accuracy.

Figure 1: Experimental setup

III. Results and discussion

The microstructural analysis of austenitic stainless steels 304 and 304L, as depicted in Fig. 2, revealed key features relevant to machinability. The microstructures showed polygonal austenite grains with annealing twins and fine lines of delta ferrite, particularly in the edge zones. The edge zone demonstrated a higher concentration of hardening structures compared to the core, with a notable difference in grain size and presence of non-metallic inclusions like manganese sulfides and calcium aluminates. In detail, the grain sizes varied significantly across different variants. For example, Variant 1 had grain sizes ranging from $G = 2$ to $G = 6$ in the core, while Variant 2 exhibited a grain size of $G = 4$ in the edge zone and coarser sizes in the core. Variant 3 showed uniform grain sizes ($G = 5-6$), and Variants 5 and 6 had similar sizes ($G = 3-4$) in both zones. These differences are attributed to variations in cooling rates, impurities, and processing methods, impacting the mechanical properties and performance of the materials.

Figure 2: Comparison of the microstructure of the investigated austenitic stainless steels at the surface or edge and core of the specimens

The compositional analysis, highlighted that Variant 6, with high sulfur and manganese content, improved machinability by facilitating chip formation and reducing tool wear, though excessive sulfur might compromise ductility. The carbon and chromium contents in Variant 6 also contributed to higher hardness and cutting forces. The interplay among alloying elements, heat treatments, and processing conditions significantly affects machinability, underscoring the complexity in optimizing performance. Microhardness measurements indicated that edge areas consistently had higher hardness compared to the core. Variant 3 exhibited the most significant hardness variation, with the highest edge hardness but the lowest core hardness. This variation, influenced by alloy composition and processing effects, such as strain gradients, affects the material's machinability.

Residual stress analysis (Fig. 3) revealed that peeled variants (5 and 6) had higher tensile residual stresses at the surface but transitioned to compressive stresses deeper, aiding in chip formation. The low compressive residual stresses in Variants 2 and 4 resulted in better surface quality and reduced tool wear. Surface roughness results indicated that roughness increased with feed rate. Variant 6 exhibited the highest roughness values, while Variant 1 showed consistently low values. The regression analysis highlighted feed rate, grain size at the edge, and infeed as significant factors affecting surface roughness, with grain size being a crucial parameter. Chip morphology and tool wear varied by variant. Peel variants (5 and 6) generally produced shorter, more manageable chips but led to increased tool wear. Non-peel variants often caused longer chips and more significant tool wear.

Figure 3: Residual stress of the investigated austenitic stainless steels starting from the outer area (edge zone) of the specimens into 0.5 mm distance from the surface

Variants 7 and 8, flagged for tool breakage and component distortion, had the same chemical composition and mechanical properties as variant 2 but showed significantly higher microhardness and compressive residual stresses in the edge zone. Fig. 4a highlights increased microhardness in the edge zone of these variants, while Fig. 4b shows higher compressive residual stresses up to 0.1 mm from the surface

compared to variant 1. These findings suggest that microhardness and residual stress in the edge zone are more critical factors for tool wear and component distortion than chemical composition or mechanical properties, emphasizing the influence of manufacturing processes on machinability.

Figure 4: Comparison of variants 7 and 8 with variant 1: (a) Microhardness; (b) Residual stress

IV. Conclusions

The study revealed that while chemical composition and mechanical properties did not directly correlate with machinability metrics, grain size at the edge, residual stresses, and processing methods played crucial roles in determining machinability. The results underscore the importance of manufacturing processes in influencing machinability, particularly in the context of tool wear and component distortion. The findings emphasize the need for a comprehensive understanding of microstructural features and residual stresses to optimize machining performance.

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